

Dynamic cooling of an air-cooled data center under transient workloads

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Abstract: Temporal variations in workload traffic can result in thermal throttling or overcooling depending on the thermal conditions in data centers. While the former is responsible for damaging IT equipment, the latter is responsible for increasing power consumption by the cooling system. In this study, thermal response and cooling efficiency of an operating data center are investigated under generated workload trends by means of transient Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations. Strong recirculation and cold-air leakage indicated by the simulation results reduce cooling efficiency of the data center. Variations of the maximum temperature and Rack Cooling Index Low (RCILO) are monitored for a certain time duration under various workload trends. Numerical simulation results reveal that the RCILO is a key parameter for detecting overcooling in an air-cooled data center and the cooling system should be sensitive to the transient variations of workloads. Recirculation and leakage effects are investigated using newly developed metrics. Numerical simulations revealed that the power consumption by the cooling can be reduced by 10% when dynamic cooling approach was adopted.

Keywords: data center; transient workload; dynamic cooling; CFD

1. Introduction

Digitalization of life, education, and work resulted in a drastic increase in IT demand over the globe, especially during the pandemic period. Data centers (DCs) have been generally subjected to transient workloads to meet a huge demand for increased digitalization in the last decade. Steady-state analysis of a data center may not reflect actual thermal response under transient workloads since thermal structure of an air-cooled data center is inherently dynamic due to the temporal variations in the workload traffic. Detecting overcooling in a data center is fundamental to reducing energy consumption by cooling since most of the data centers may be subjected to overcooling due to the dynamic behavior of the workload traffic.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models have been effectively used as a promising approach for the thermal design of data centers based on the simulations of flow and thermal structures in the last decade. However, most of the numerical studies available in the literature lack capturing transient effects due to their steady-state assumptions. Only a few studies in the literature have focused on the capturing of dynamic thermal structures in air-cooled DCs. Jonas et al. [1] proposed a thermal model creating a discontinuity in the DC to capture transient responses. Ghosh and Joshi [2] developed a dynamic performance optimized data center model for the prediction of the thermal response under a transient startup scenario focusing on the development and implementation of an improved method to characterize nonlinear behavior for real-time control and optimization of the energy consumption. The proposed method was found to be unsuitable for solving a multivariate problem when transient flow and temperature

domains exist. Fulpagare et al. [3] compared simulated and measured temperature variations at the outlet of the racks under transient load conditions. A similar trend was observed from both experimental and CFD studies by increasing heat sources during a specified time duration. Combination of the inlet heat load and rack outlet temperature was found to be useful for data-driven modeling of data centers. Erden et al. [4] determined transient thermal features of servers by temperature measurements inside a DC. An experimental study was carried out and validated to determine server time constant and thermal capacitance, which can be used for the solution of the unsteady heat equation for a server using black-box model. Rao et al. [5] investigated effects of thermal constraints on the performance and power of multi-core processors. They proposed various expressions for the maximum number of cores that can be used with and without throttling, the transition from single-core to multi-core and the total power consumption calculation based on the power and thermal models. It was seen that the reduction in the server performance due to the thermal restrictions in the models might cause inefficient cooling. Instructions are sent randomly to a DC in general to run multiple processes at the same time. Zhou et al. [6] proposed load balancing algorithms to preserve computing performance including sequential and the shortest job concepts. Algorithms considered thermal throttling in the DC using various parameters such as overall response time and processing time to stabilize workload traffic in certain situations. Bogdan et al. [7] investigated the energy efficiency provided by heterogeneous multicore architectures in computing. They presented scheduling for low-power and mobile processors used in micro servers. The proposed technique has increased efficiency in power consumption and provided system decisions that avoid thermal throttling. Weissel and Bellosa [8] proposed a method to determine thermal throttling and shutdown at the DC level as a result of increased heat densities when thermal limits are exceeded. CPU cycles were counted for energy characterization and throttling was investigated according to the runtime. In addition, tasks were automatically throttled with task-specific temperature management according to their effects on the temperature rise. In order to minimize performance loss, Huang et al. [9] introduced a compact thermal model called HotSpot for the adaptation of throttling effects to time-varying workload traffic. Jain et al. [10] examined the use of powerful and heterogeneous multicores in micro servers with a new scheduling policy for heterogeneous micro servers to optimize performance metrics such as average response time and service level agreements ensuring thermally safe operation. Aforementioned studies indicate that the thermal throttling of IT equipment still remains a huge challenge in DCs and can be detected by time variation of the thermal data. This work considers an air-cooled data center for the investigation of the dynamic thermal effects by means of transient CFD simulations under various workload trends. Cooling efficiency of the DC is evaluated with respect to the Rack Cooling Index (RCI). New metrics are also proposed to capture recirculation effects and leakage in open aisle DCs. Time variations of maximum temperature inside the DC, maximum rack inlet temperature and metrics are evaluated for the detection of the thermal throttling and over cooling. The cooling system of the DC has been upgraded to a dynamic cooling system considering dynamic behavior of the workload traffic. Energy efficiency gained by the dynamic cooling is evaluated to show reliability of the proposed cooling approach.

2. Configuration of the Data Center

The DC located at Syracuse University was studied as a case study in the current work. As shown in Fig. 1, the server room has a raised floor with dimensions of 7.89 m \times 5.64 m and the room height is 3.66 m. The DC has three power racks with dimensions of 0.61 m width, 0.997 m long and 2 m height. Two Computer Room Air Handler (CRAH) units are located inside the room for the cooling of hot air exhausted from IT equipment. Dimensions of the CRAH1 and CRAH2 are 0.889 m \times 1.880 \times 1.98 m and 0.953 m \times 1.880 m \times 1.98 m, respectively. Hot air is

sucked through the inlet of the CRAH1 and supplied from the floor to the room with a flow rate of $3.04 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

Fig. 1. Three-dimensional sketch of the open-aisle DC.

Four servers are deployed at each rack with different power consumption and flow rates (Table 1). Cold air supplied from the bottom is directed to the servers by the server fans and hot air exhausted from the servers is cooled down by the CRAH1 (Fig. 1.) Servers are labeled from the bottom to the top of the rack as a conventional approach adopted in the DC community. Explicit energy sources are assigned to the cell zones inside the servers and momentum sources are defined at each server to set fan driven flow [11, 12] in the numerical model.

Table 1

Power consumptions and flow rates of the servers.

Server	Power Consumption [W]	Q [m^3/s]
R1S1	3720	0.31
R1S2	3720	0.31
R1S3	3840	0.32
R1S4	3720	0.31
R2S1	3645.83	0.35
R2S2	3645.83	0.35
R2S3	3854.17	0.37
R2S4	3854.17	0.37
R3S1	3809.52	0.32
R3S2	3690.48	0.31
R3S3	3809.52	0.32
R3S4	3690.48	0.31

3. Computational Model

3.1 Governing Equations

Buoyancy-driven compressible and turbulent flow inside the DC can be represented by the following unsteady continuity, momentum and energy equations:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho u_i) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho u_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho u_i u_j) = \frac{-\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] + \rho g_i + S_i \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho h)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho u_j h) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_i} \right] \quad (3)$$

Where ρ is the density of the fluid, u_i is the mean velocity component in the i -direction, t is the time, p is the pressure, x_i and x_j are the Cartesian coordinates, g_i is the gravitational acceleration in the i -direction, h is the Favre-averaged enthalpy, S_i is the momentum source, μ and μ_t are molecular and turbulent viscosities, respectively. Molecular viscosity is calculated using the Sutherland viscosity model [11] and the turbulent viscosity can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\nu_t = \frac{a_1 k}{\max(a_1 \omega, SF_2)} \quad (4)$$

In the present study, the $k - \omega$ Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence closure model is used to account for adverse pressure gradients and boundary layer effects near the walls [13]. Turbulence kinetic energy and specific rate of dissipation are determined from the solutions of the following transport equations:

$$\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[(\nu + \sigma_k \nu_t) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i} \right] + P - \beta k \omega \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[(\nu + \sigma_\omega \nu_t) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_i} \right] + \alpha S^2 - \beta \omega^2 + 2(1 - F_1) \frac{\sigma_{\omega 2}}{\omega} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_i} \quad (6)$$

Coefficients that appear in the equations above can be found in the literature [14]. Servers and tiles may result in significant pressure losses in the airflow. The Darcy-Forchheimer porosity model is employed to model inertial and viscous resistance by the porous medium. The following source term is calculated and added to the momentum equations to represent corresponding pressure drops:

$$S_i = - \left(\nu D + \frac{1}{2} F |u_i| \right) u_i \quad (7)$$

The Darcy and Forchheimer coefficients can be calculated from the following empirical equations [14]:

$$D = 120 \frac{(1 - p^2)}{((1 - p^3) D h^2)} \quad (8)$$

$$F = 2.3 \frac{(1-p)}{((1-p^3)Dh)} \quad (9)$$

The porosity ratio p is set to 56% and 25% for servers and floor opening, respectively, Dh is the hydraulic diameter calculated at the inlets of the server and tile [15]. The numerical model adopted in the present study was validated with the experimental measurements [11-12, 16-17] and can be used in the present study reliably.

3.2 Efficiency metrics

Thermal and cooling efficiencies of a DC can be assessed in a systematic manner according to the efficiency metrics. Inlet temperature of the server is expected to be equal to the temperature of the cold air supplied by the cooling unit under ideal condition where hot and cold regions are completely isolated with no leakage. Vast majority of the data centers experience to the leakage of the cold air where cold air supplied by the cooling unit transfers to the hot region without passing through the servers. The rack cooling index high (RCI_{HI}) and rack cooling index low (RCI_{LO}) metrics can capture servers where the inlet temperature is higher than the maximum recommended temperature and lower than the minimum recommended temperature, respectively:

$$RCI_{HI} = \left[1 - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n (T_i - T_{max-rec})}{n \times (T_{max-all} - T_{max-rec})} \right] \times 100\% \quad (10)$$

$$RCI_{LO} = \left[1 - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n (T_{min-rec} - T_i)}{n \times (T_{min-rec} - T_{min-all})} \right] \times 100\% \quad (11)$$

Where T_i is the inlet temperature of the i^{th} server, n is the number of servers, $T_{max-rec}$ is the maximum recommended temperature, $T_{min-rec}$ is the minimum recommended temperature, $T_{max-all}$ is the maximum allowable temperature and $T_{min-all}$ is the minimum allowable temperature [18, 19]. Deviation of the RCI_{LO} from 100% indicates over cooling, which results in an increase in the cooling power consumption. Recirculation effects observed above the racks result in the deviation of the RCI_{HI} from 100%.

Inlet temperature of a server is anticipated to be identical to the supply temperature of the cooling. However, temperature of the air supplied by the cooling unit decreases before the cold air reaches inlets of the servers due to the recirculation effects. The following recirculation index (RI) is proposed for the assessment of the recirculation effects in an air-cooled DC:

$$RI = \left[1 - \left(\frac{T_{rackinlet,mean} - T_{supply,CRAH}}{T_{supply,CRAH}} \right) \right] \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

Where $T_{rackinlet,mean}$ is the mean temperature at the inlet of the rack and $T_{supply,CRAH}$ is the supply temperature of the CRAH unit. Deviation of the RI from 100% indicates a measure of the recirculation effects. The RI value below 100% indicates mixing of the cold air with the hot air until it reaches inlet of a server. Air supplied from the cooling unit mixes with cooler air until it reaches the server inlet when the RI value exceeds 100%.

Leakage of the cold air through a rack results in a reduction in the outlet temperature of the corresponding server. The following metric is proposed for the detection of the cold-air leakage through the rack consisting of small gaps that allow cold air to pass to the hot region:

$$LI = \left[1 - \left(\frac{T_{rackoutlet,min} - T_{return,CRAH}}{T_{rackoutlet,min}} \right) \right] \times 100\% \quad (13)$$

Where $T_{rackoutlet,min}$ is the minimum outlet temperature observed at a server of the rack. Deviation of the LI from 100% associates with the leakage effect, which has a significant role in reducing cooling efficiency and increasing cooling power consumption in a DC.

3.3 Thermal Simulation of the DC

Numerical model solves unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equations for the simulation of turbulent flow considering buoyancy effects. Numerical simulations are performed using an open-source computational model dataCenterDST© developed based on OpenFoam libraries for the thermal simulations of air [12, 16] and liquid-cooled [20] DCs. Comparison of the simulated and measured temperature profiles at the rears of the racks indicated that the present model was capable of capturing eddies and buoyancy effects [16], as well as resultant thermal structure spatially and temporally. Unsteady terms of the governing equations were discretized using first-order accurate Euler scheme, convective terms were discretized using first-order accurate upwind scheme and divergence terms were discretized using second-order accurate Gauss linear scheme. Coefficients calculated from the discretization of the governing equations are stored into the matrices and corresponding matrices are solved using the Preconditioned bi-conjugate gradient (PBiCGStab) algorithm. Maximum Courant number was set to 4 for the buoyantPimpleFoam solver, which achieves a stable solution for the PIMPLE algorithm as a combination of PISO (Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operator) and SIMPLE (Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations) algorithms. Numerical simulations were performed using parallel computing with the ipmi on the micro-data center located at Empa [21].

Fig. 2 visualizes streamlines at the regions where temperature is lower than the recommended minimum temperature (Fig. 2a) and higher than the recommended maximum temperature (Fig. 2b) to combine thermal and flow structures at a single visual. It is clearly seen in Fig. 2a that most of the cold air supplied from the tile is directed to the CRAH1 without passing through the servers, which is the evidence of cold air leakage. Recirculation of hot air observed near the ceiling and rear of the CRAH2 reduces thermal efficiency of the DC. Servers at the bottom of the racks are devoid of any hot points even though having identical power consumptions with the servers at the top of the racks. Thus, high workloads should be allocated to the servers near the bottom.

Fig. 2. Visualization of the streamlines at regions where (a) air temperature is lower than the recommended minimum temperature and (b) higher than the recommended maximum temperature.

3.4 Transient Workloads

Various workload trends are considered in Fig. 3 to monitor thermal response of the DC to the sudden changes in the utilization rates. Durations of the workloads are set to 250 s during 750 s total simulation duration to observe stabilization of the thermal structure, which depends on the thermal characteristics of the DC itself. While Working Scenario 1 (WS1) and WS3 show sudden drop and increase, respectively, WS5 depicts a continuous increase in the workload traffic. As can be seen in Fig. 3, WS2, WS4 and WS6 were designed to see the effect of the magnitude of the change in the utilization rates.

Fig. 3. Time variations of workload trends (a) WS1, (b) WS2, (c) WS3, (d) WS4, (e) WS5 and (f) WS6.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Transient variations of the thermal characteristics

Fig. 4 shows variations of the maximum air temperature with time at the DC for the working scenarios defined in Fig. 3. Sudden drops in workloads at WS1 and WS2 resulted in about 13 °C and 20 °C in Fig. 4a when the total power consumption reduced from 100% to 50% and 25%, respectively, which were found to be significant. Similar trends were observed at the comparison of WS3 and WS4 in Fig. 4b. However, increasing total IT load (WS3 and WS4) resulted in a higher temperature jump than that of decreasing IT load (WS1 and WS2), which may be due to the strong recirculation effects observed in Fig. 2. Continues increasing and decreasing of IT loads defined for WS5 and WS6, respectively, influenced the maximum temperature at the same forms as in the time variations of the IT loads. Supply temperature of a CRAH unit at a DC is adjusted mainly according to the local temperature measured by the temperature sensors located at certain locations. Results shown in Fig. 4 prove that the selection of the measurement point is critical for the effective and reliable cooling of the IT equipment.

Fig. 4. Time variations of the maximum air for (a) WS1 and WS2, (b) WS3 and WS4 and (c) WS5 and WS6.

Fig. 5 compares time variations of the RCI_{LO} of the workload trends. Deviations of the RCI_{LO} from 100% at the initial stages clearly indicate that the DC is operated under over cooling conditions. Overcooling increased when the total IT load was reduced to 25% and the maximum air temperature experiences a periodic variation due to low IT loads.

Fig. 5. Time variations of the RCI_{LO} for (a) WS1 and WS2, (b) WS3 and WS4 and (c) WS5 and WS6.

4.2 Recirculation and leakage indexes

Variations of the RI and LI indexes are given for various working scenarios and total IT loads in Table 2. Deviation of the RI from 100% and recirculation effects increase as the IT load increases. Thus, DC experiences high recirculation effects for increasing workloads since the cold air supplied from the cooling unit cannot reach the inlet of the upper servers. On the other hand, deviations of the LI from 100% was found to be identical since workloads are not effective on the LI as much as in the RI.

Table 2

Calculated RI and LI metrics for working scenarios.

WS	Workload (%)	RI (%)	LI (%)
WS1	100	71.215	101.869
	25	91.972	98.486
	100	69.929	99.443
WS2	100	71.215	101.865
	50	85.770	99.531
	100	70.8	101.199
WS3	25	92.336	98.541
	100	70.879	100.441
	25	92.236	99.068
WS4	50	85.579	99.299
	100	70.4	100.646
	50	85.722	99.417
WS5	25	92.336	98.564
	50	85.143	98.375
	100	70.479	101.178
WS6	100	71.215	101.869
	50	85.772	99.556
	25	91.993	98.198

4.3. Effect of the dynamic cooling

Simulation results and calculated RCI_{LO} indicated that the DC experienced to overcooling. Numerical simulations are performed for WS6 using various supply temperatures of the CRAH unit. Fig. 6 shows variations of the RCI_{LO} and RCI_{HI} for the supply temperature of 14, 16 and 18 °C. The RCI_{LO} approaches 100% when the supply temperature is 18 °C and overcooling can be mitigated for the present working scenario. On the other hand, the RCI_{HI} deviates from the 100% when the supply temperature increases since high supply temperature will influence hot points observed near the top of the racks (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Variations of the (a) RCI_{LO} and (b) RCI_{HI} metrics for different supply temperatures in WS6.

Fig. 7a shows temperate distribution at a vertical plane defined at the rear of the rack for the supply temperature of 18°C . Inlet temperatures of the servers distributed at the top of the racks increase due to the increasing supply temperature. Moreover, inlet temperatures are found to be lower than the maximum allowable temperatures [22]. Thus, adjusted supply temperature is the optimal value for both avoiding overcooling and reliable operation of the IT equipment. Nevertheless, it should be ensured that the chip temperatures of those servers should be kept below the threshold value recommended by the server manufacturer. Fig. 7b shows variation of the inlet temperature of the server, where the maximum inlet temperature was observed in Fig. 7a.

Fig. 7. (a) Temperature distribution at a vertical plane located 0.3 m behind the racks for $T_{supp}=18$ °C and (b) variation of the inlet temperature of Rack3Fr4 for different supply temperatures in WS6.

Cooling load on the CRAH can be calculated from the following energy equation:

$$q = \dot{m}C_p\Delta T \quad (14)$$

Where q is the heat load, \dot{m} is the mass flux of the air, ΔT is the temperature difference between inlet and outlet of the CRAH and C_p is the specific heat capacity. Cooling loads on the CRAH are calculated for the supply temperatures of 14 °C and 18 °C and compared in Table 4. Note that the flow rate of the supplied air is kept for both cases. The energy saving is found to be 3.19 MJ when the supply temperature increases from 14 °C to 18 °C during 750 s.

Table 4. Variations of the cooling load for WS6.

T_{supply} (°C)	%100 Workload	%50 Workload	%25 Workload
14	54161 W	32113 W	14496 W
18	52186 W	31185 W	13145 W

Previous analysis proves that the supply temperature of the CRAH should be optimized according to total workload. On the other hand, supply temperature should be adjusted according the variations of the workloads as a dynamic cooling approach. To this end, supply temperature of the cooling device is optimized according to the changes in workloads. Numerical simulation results for WS6 indicate that the supply temperatures of 18, 23 and 30 °C maintain reliably thermal conditions according to the standards. Table 5 shows variations of supply temperatures and corresponding cooling loads when a dynamic cooling approach is adopted. Results indicate that the power consumption by the cooling can be reduced by 10% when a dynamic cooling approach is used.

Table 5. Dynamically changing supply temperature with workload change

Workload (%)	T_{supply} (°C)	Heat load on the cooling unit
100	18	52186 W
50	23	26529 W
25	30	12479 W

5. Conclusions

Thermal field of an open-aisle data center is investigated by a validated open-source computational model. Recirculation effects and cold air by-pass indicated by the high-resolution numerical simulations significantly reduce cooling efficiency of the data center. Efficiency of the data center is monitored with respect to the RCI_{LO} , which is a widely used metric in the literature. In addition to that, two metrics are proposed for the detection of recirculation and leakage effects. Time variations of thermal and cooling characteristics are monitored under different workload trends to reveal transient workload effects on the thermal structure of a data center. The cooling system is then modified to a dynamic cooling system, in which supply temperature of the cooler is optimized according to the workloads. Comparison of static and dynamic cooling approaches indicates that the power consumption by the cooling can be reduced by 10% when the cooling system is upgraded to a dynamic cooling approach. The cooling system will be managed at optimal conditions using Modbus communication system depending on the workload traffic for the practical implementation of the dynamic cooling system in the future study.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Nomenclature

ρ	Density of the fluid (kg/m ³)
u_i	Mean velocity component in the i -direction (m/s)
t	Time (s)
p	Pressure (Pa)
x_i, x_j	Cartesian coordinates (m)
g_i	Gravitational acceleration in the i -direction (m/s ²)
h	Favre-averaged enthalpy
S_i	Momentum source
μ, μ_t	Molecular and turbulent viscosities (m ² /s)
Q	Flow rate (m ³ /s)
Φ	Porosity of the server
D_h	Hydraulic diameter defined at the inlet of the server (m)
D	Darcy coefficient
F	Forcheimer coefficient
U	Velocity (m/s)
T	Temperature (°C)
p_{rgh}	Dynamic pressure (Pa)
LI	Leakage Index
$T_{max-rec}$	Maximum recommended temperature (°C)
$T_{min-rec}$	Minimum recommended temperature (°C)
$T_{max-all}$	Maximum allowable temperature (°C)
$T_{max-all}$	Maximum allowable temperature (°C)
RCI	Rack Cooling Index
RI	Recirculation Index
WS	Working Scenario

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